

Table 2. Effect of N on grain yield,^a Aduthurai, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	1.4 c
40	1.8 b
80	2.0 a
120	2.1 a

^aAverage of all varieties.

yield (Table 1). N level did not influence RTV, but significantly influenced grain yield. Highest yield was with 120 kg

N/ha, which was at par with yield at 80 kg N/ha (Table 2). N × varietal interaction was not significant. *ℓ*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Seed dormancy in rice varieties

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Dormancy of seeds within the same panicle varies with spikelet position on the panicle. We studied within-panicle dormancy patterns of 10 popular kharif rices at ARS in 1982 kharif. Panicles were collected at harvest and divided equally into top, middle, and bottom parts. They were sown in soil and watered as necessary.

Dormancy was lowest in the top 1/3

Seed dormancy at different spikelet levels within rice panicles, Maruteru, India.

Variety	Dormant seeds (%)			Variety	Dormant seeds (%)		
	Top	Middle	Bottom		Top	Middle	Bottom
MTU5293	50	60	90	MTU5182	40	70	90
MTU2716	40	70	90	MTU2400	40	70	90
MTU2077	60	50	90	BPT11503	50	70	80
MTU4569	40	70	90	PLA1100	50	70	80
MTU5201	40	65	95	Mean	46	66.5	88.5
MTU2067	50	70	80	CD (5%): V : ns		P = 3	V × P : ns
				CV (%): 15.3			

of panicles and gradually increased in the middle and bottom parts (see table). This was attributed to the different age of seeds at different panicle levels.

Anthesis and fertilization occur in an acropetal succession; therefore the top spikelets are fertilized earliest and are oldest. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

High yielding, semidwarf, blast (BI)-resistant NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 for southern Andhra Pradesh

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NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 were developed for B1 resistance and suitable grain quality for southern Andhra Pradesh. NLR9672-96 is a secondary selection from NLR9672, from Bulk H/9 and Milekkunning. NLR27999 was selected from a segregating generation of RP31-49-2/BCP 1. Milekkunning and RP31-49-2 were parents for B1

Table 1. Yield attributes of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999, Nellore, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	1000-grain weight (g)
NLR27999	160-170	113	289	291	22
NLR9672-96	150-160	119	282	301	21
NLR9672	150-160	100	248	339	23
NLR9674	160-170	104	269	326	22

resistance. NLR9672-96 matures in 150-160 d and NLR27999 in 160-170 d. Both are weakly photoperiod sensitive and have short, bold grains with dirty brown glumes. Milled rice is white and translucent, and meets local consumer requirements. Threshability of both varieties is good, and both shed fewer

grains than locally grown NLR9672. Both have seed dormancy at maturity and lodging resistance. NLR9672-96 has a droopy flag leaf and NLR27999 an erect, medium flag leaf.

The varieties are moderately resistant to leaf and neck B1 and bacterial blight and resistant to brown planthopper.